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Research Article

PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS AND *IN VITRO* ANTIOXIDANT AND ANTIDIABETIC ACTIVITIES OF *Melastomastrum capitatum* (VAHL.) FERN. (*MELASTOMATACEAE*) LEAF EXTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Melastomastrum capitatum (Vahl.) Fern. is a shrub found in wet areas in the Mambilla Plateau and Southern parts of Nigeria. The leaf has been used as a cure for many diseases such as cancer, diabetes, inflammations and other diseases. In an attempt to provide scientific justification for the antidiabetic and antioxidant potentials, the present study was carried out. The phytochemical and metallic contents were evaluated using standard procedures, antioxidant activity was evaluated by DPPH and ABTS radical scavenging assays while *in vitro* antidiabetic activity was evaluated by glucose uptake by yeast cells method. Phytochemical screening showed the presence of alkaloids, saponins, phytosterols, tannins, flavonoids, and terpenoids in the extracts. The high amount of aluminium (Al) metal was detected with a value of 1682.14 mg/kg while other metals such as Mg, Na, and K are between 24.16 to 76.11 mg/kg. Among the three extracts, ethyl acetate (EF) exhibited the highest antidiabetic and antioxidant activities followed by methanol extract (MF). The EF showed also the highest total phenolic content (TPC) and total flavonoid contents (TFC) of 80.10 ± 2.01 mg GAE/g and 45.25 ± 1.01 mg RE/g respectively while the MF had 58.92 ± 1.01 mg GAE/g and 25.14 ± 1.02 mg RE/g respectively. Also, the EF exhibited a 72.14% of DPPH scavenging activity reduction and 69.03% of ABTS scavenging activity reduction at 800 μ g/mL. A concentration-dependent *in vitro* antidiabetic activity was shown in glucose uptake of yeast cells with the highest glucose uptake of 80.10 mM seen in the EF. This value was significant ($p < 0.05$) when compared to the control metronidazole at concentrations of 2.5 to 40 μ g/mL. The study showed that *M. capitatum* leaf extracts possess antioxidant and antidiabetic activities which affirm the use of the plant in folkloric medicine.

Keywords: *Melastomastrum capitatum*; Antioxidant; Antidiabetic; Phenolics; Yeast cells.

INTRODUCTION

Natural products derived from medicinal plants have gained significant recognition in the potential management of several clinical conditions, including cancer [1]. Much research has been geared towards the evaluation of plant extracts as prophylactic agents, which offer great potential to inhibit the pain signal process. Simultaneously, the synergistic effects of the cocktail of plant metabolites and the multiple points of intervention offer higher efficacy during chemoprevention regimens [2]. The Interest in investigating the medicinal values of plants to explore new arsenals against the threat of new and recent diseases is increasing constantly throughout the world, especially in Asia and Africa. Various features of plants such as economic feasibility, low toxicity, fewer side effects and potent pharmacological activities contribute to their increasing popularity [3]. However, numerous lead compounds have been discovered in plants till now. In addition, more than 30% of global pharmacological preparations are plant-based [4]. Although analgesics are essential to many living organisms to restore the organism to normal biological processes, continuous generation of oxygen-centered free radicals and other reactive oxygen species *in vivo* causes cell death and tissue damage [5]. Oxidative damage done by free radicals causes the pathogenesis of many deadly diseases like cancer, Alzheimer's and diabetes [6–8].

Diabetes mellitus is caused by inherited and/or acquired deficiency in the production of insulin by the pancreas or by the ineffectiveness of the insulin [9]. This insulin deficiency results in an increased concentration of glucose in the blood increase in blood glucose damages many of the body's systems particularly, the blood vessels and nerves. Hyperglycemia caused due to decreased insulin production is called Type-1 diabetes and hyperglycemia due to insufficient insulin production utilization is called Type-2 diabetes [9]. Out of these two types, Type- diabetes is a major problem of today and it accounts for nearly 95% of the total diabetic population of about 246 million [10].

Since ancient times, plants have been an exemplary source of medicine Ayurveda and other Nigerian literature mention the use of plants in the treatment of various human ailments. Nigeria has about 45,000 plant species and among them, several thousand have been claimed to possess medicinal properties [11]. The commonly practised treatment of diabetes includes oral anti-diabetic drugs, insulin injection and management through diet and physical exercise. Apart from the currently available therapeutic means for the treatment of diabetes, traditional plant medicines are more used throughout the world for the treatment of diabetes [11]. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), the global prevalence of diabetes is estimated to increase from 4% in 1995 to 5.4% by the year 2025 mostly in developing countries. Nigeria presently is among the country that has the largest number of diabetic patients in the world and has been infamously known as the diabetic capital of the world [11]. Resistance of Type-2 diabetes, but these drugs fail to significantly alter the course of diabetic complications and have limited use because of undesirable side effects and high rate of secondary failure, the drugs are sulfonylureas, biguanide, a thiazolidinedione, and glycoside inhibitors are widely used to control the hyperglycemia, hyperlipidemia and insulin [12].

Free radical reactions are one of the major causes of diseases, particularly in developed and developing nations [13]. Diseases such as cancer and rancidity of foods are believed to be caused by these reactive oxygen species (ROS). Natural and synthetic antioxidants are usually used to reduce the effects of these radicals. It has been reported that synthetically-derived antioxidants often contain toxic and adverse reactions to the body [14]. It is therefore recommended that plant-derived antioxidants or plant-based antioxidants should be alternatives. Many medicinal plants are sources of natural antioxidants because they possess metabolites such as flavonoids, alkaloids, terpenoids and phenolics. In Nigeria, many medicinal plants with antioxidant potentials used in traditional medicine have been well documented and others are still being screened for their antioxidant activities [4].

The plant *Melastomastrum capitatum* is a dicot plant belonging to the family *Melastomataceae*. It is locally called *Belkon* in the Fulani language in Nigeria's North-East, Taraba State. Anti-inflammatory and analgesic activity as well as anti-hypercholesterolemic of the leaf methanol extract in albino mice has been reported [15]. The leaf crude extract contains mainly glycosides, alkaloids, tannins and carbohydrates [15]. Other uses of the plant in traditional medicine include its use as an anti-rheumatic agent, cure stomach aches, blood purification, management of diuresis, intestinal and correcting pulmonary problems. A large part of the plant has a sweet-to-sour taste. The leaves are used as an anti-rheumatic agent, cure stomach aches purification of blood vesicles and blood as well as for alleviating diuresis (leaf sap) and sedatives. The leaf methanol extract possesses analgesic and anti-inflammatory activities in mice and the plant was very safe as an ethno-medicinal prescription in traditional medicine. The leaf extract is used to correct pulmonary and intestinal problems [16]. A report by Ukwubile *et al.* [15], showed that the leaf can lower blood cholesterol levels thereby promoting good cholesterol in the mice. A similar report showed that the leaf can

successfully act as an analgesic drug when loaded in exosomes in mice thereby reducing pain than when delivered in ordinary [17].

This current study was carried out to determine the presence of major plant secondary metabolites and evaluate the *in vitro* antidiabetic and antioxidant activities of *Melastomastrum capitatum* leaf extracts.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection and Identification of Plant

Fresh leaves of *Melastomastrum capitatum* were collected in the evening hours from Mambila Plateau Sardauna L.G.A of Taraba State in December 2023 and were identified by Dr. C. A. Ukwubile of the Department of Pharmacognosy, Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Maiduguri, Nigeria where a voucher specimen number UMM/FPH/MEA/001 was deposited for the plant in the herbarium.

Preparation and Extraction of Plant Materials

The fresh leaves of *M. Capitatum* were shade-dried for two weeks and reduced into a fine powder using an electronic blender (M500, Japan). The ground powder weighing 1600 g (1.6 kg) was then extracted using 2.5 L of methanol (MF) by cold maceration technique, and then sequentially partitioned using n-hexane (HF) and ethyl acetate (EF). The extracts were separately filtered using a Whatman number 1 filter paper. The filtrates were then concentrated *in vacuo* at room temperature using a rotary evaporator (ThermoFisher, UK), to obtain a dark-green extract for each fraction that was stored in clean sample bottles for further use. The percentage yield was then calculated from the formula below:

$$\% \text{ yield of extracts} = \text{Final weight of extract} / \text{Initial weight of powdered leaves} \times 100 \quad (\text{i})$$

Phytochemical Analysis of *M. capitatum* Leaf Extracts

The qualitative phytochemical constituents of leaf extracts were carried out following standard procedures to identify the presence or absence of metabolites such as alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, cardiac glycosides, tannins, anthraquinones, fats/oils, phytosterols and triterpenoids [18]. The following tests were carried out for the phytochemical analysis:

Test for glycosides (general test): To a portion of the extract, 5 mL of dilute H₂SO₄ was added and boiled in a water bath for 10-15 min. It was cooled and neutralized with 20% KOH. It was then divided into two portions;

- i. to the first portion, 5 mL of a mixture of Fehling's solution A and B was added and boiled, and a brick-red precipitate showed the release of reducing sugar as a result of the hydrolysis of glycosides.
- ii. to the second portion, about 3 mL of ferric chloride solution was added, and a green to blue colour was produced because phenolic aglycones were released due to the hydrolysis [19].

Test for free anthraquinones

Bontrager's test: To 0.5 g of the extract in a dry test tube, 5 mL of chloroform was added and shaken for at least 5 min. This was filtered and the filtrate was shaken with an equal volume of 10% ammonia solution. Bright pink colour in the aqueous (at the upper layer) indicates the presence of free anthraquinones.

Test for steroids/triterpenes

Liebermann-Buchard's test: To 0.5 g of the extract, an equal volume of acetic acid anhydride was added and mixed gently. 1 mL of concentrated H₂SO₄ was added down the side of the test tube to form a lower layer. Colour change was observed immediately and for 1 h. Blue to blue-green colour in the upper side and a reddish, pink or purple colour shows the presence of triterpenes.

Test for cardiac glycosides

Keller-Kiliani's test: 0.5 g of the extract was dissolved in 1 mL of glacial acetic acid containing traces of FeCl₃ solution. This was then transferred into a dry test tube and 1 mL of conc. H₂SO₄ was added down the side of the tube to form a lower layer at the bottom and observed at the interphase for a purple-brown ring. This indicates the presence of deoxy sugars and a pale- green colour in the upper acid layer shows the presence of cardiac glycosides [17].

Kedde's test: To 0.5 g of the extract, 1 mL of 2 % solution of 3, 5-dinitrobenzoic acid was added in 95% alcohol. The solution was made alkaline with 5% NaOH, appearance of a purple-blue colour, shows the presence of cardenolides.

Test for saponins

Frothing test: Exactly 10 mL of distilled water was added to a portion of the extract and was shaken vigorously for 30 sec. The tube was allowed to stand in a vertical position and was observed for 30 min. A honeycomb froth that persists for 10-15 min revealed the presence of saponins.

Test for tannins

Ferric-chloride test: To 0.5 g of the extract, 3 drops of ferric chloride solution were added. A greenish-black precipitate indicates the presence of condensed tannins while hydrolysable tannins give a blue or brownish-blue precipitate.

Lead sub-acetate test: To 0.5 g of the extract, 3 drops of lead sub-acetate solution were added. A colour precipitate reveals the presence of tannins.

Test of flavonoids

Shinoda's test: 0.5 g of the extract was dissolved in 2 mL of 50% methanol in the heat metallic magnesium chips and a few drops of conc. HCl were added. The appearance of red colour shows the presence of flavonoids.

NaOH test: Two drops of 10% NaOH were added to 0.5 g of extract. Yellow colouration shows the presence of flavonoids.

Test for alkaloids

Dragendorff's test: To 0.5 g of the extract, two drops of Dragendorff's reagent were added. A reddish-brown precipitate shows the presence of alkaloids.

Picric acid test: One drop of 1% picric acid solution were added to 0.5 g of the extract in a test tube, yellow coloration shows the presence of alkaloids.

Wagner's test: Two drops of Wagner's reagent were added to 0.5 g of the extract's whitish precipitate revealing the presence of alkaloids [20].

Total phenolic contents (TPC)

The total phenolic content was determined using the Folin-Ciocalteu (FC) method with slight modifications. Briefly, the FC stock solution was prepared by dissolving 10 g of FC in 10 mL deionized water (i.e., 1:10) before the commencement of the experiment. Similarly, 7.5 % (w/v) Na₂CO₃ was dissolved in 10 mL of deionized water, while the stock solution of extract was prepared by dissolving 10 g of the extract in 10 mL of 98.1 % (v/v) methanol (1000 µg/mL). After this, the three stock solutions were all mixed and allowed to stand for 6 min. In the same way, a gallic acid (500 µg/mL) standard solution was prepared and the concentrations of 0 to 150 µg/mL were used as diluting concentrations for plotting gallic acid calibration curve [21]. The absorbance of each solution was taken at 765 nm using the UV-Vis spectrophotometer (ThermoFisher, UK). The concentration of gallic acid (GA) in each extract was then calculated from the linear equation from the calibration curve using their absorbance. The TPC was then calculated and expressed as mg GAE/g using the formula below:

$$TPC = C \times V/m \quad (ii)$$

Where TPC is total phenolic contents (in mg gallic acid equivalent; GAE per gram), C is the gallic acid concentration (but C = x/1000 mg/g), V is the volume of the extract per solvent (i.e., 1 mL) and m is the weight of extract (in gram).

Determination of flavonoid contents (TFC)

The TFC of the extract was evaluated using an aluminium chloride (AlCl₃) colourimetry assay with slight modifications. Briefly, 0.5 mL of the avocado methanol seed extract was added to a test tube containing 2 mL of 98.1 % (v/v) methanol. To the test tube, 3 mL of 10 % NaNO₂ was added and kept in the dark for 5 min. Then 3 mL of 10 % AlCl₃ was added to the mixture and left for 1 min. Thereafter, 1 mL of 1 M NaOH solution was added and made up to 5 mL volume with distilled water and kept for 10 min. Finally, the absorbance of the solution was measured at 510 nm [22]. Rutin was used as standard and the result obtained for TFC was expressed as mg rutin equivalent per gram of the sample (mg RE/ g). The concentrations of rutin were taken from 25 to 800 µg/mL. The TFC was derived from the rutin standard curve and calculated from the formula below. All the readings were taken in triplicates.

$$TFC = C \times V/m \quad (iii)$$

Where TFC is total flavonoid contents (in mg rutin equivalent; RE per gram), C is rutin concentration (but $C = x/1000$ mg/g), V is the volume of the extract per solvent (i.e., 1 mL) and m is the weight of extract (in gram).

Element Content Analysis of *M. capitatum* Leaf Extracts

Metallic elements were analyzed by the atomic absorption spectrophotometer (Agilent Technologies, UK) after carrying out nitric acid-perchloric acid digestion technique [19].

Evaluation of Antioxidant Activity

To evaluate the antioxidant activity of the avocado seed extract three methods namely 1,1-diphenyl-2-picryl-hydrazyl (DPPH), and 2,2'-Azino-bis (3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid) diammonium salt (ABTS) were used. Stock solutions of crude seed extract were prepared separately in methanol (10 mg/mL). These stock solutions were further diluted in distilled water into four different concentrations of 100 to 600 µg/mL. Ascorbic acid and Trolox standard solutions were also prepared similarly.

Evaluation of DPPH radical scavenging activity

The DPPH radical scavenging activity of the avocado seed methanol extract was determined using the method previously described [21], with slight modifications.

Evaluation of ABTS radical scavenging activity

In this method, ABTS radical cation was obtained by mixing 5 mM ABTS solution (Sigma Aldrich, St. Louis Mo) in 10 mL distilled water and 1 mM potassium persulfate solution in 10 mL distilled water as previously described. The percentage of ABTS scavenging was then calculated from the formula below [23]:

$$\% \text{ ABTS radical scavenging} = (AbsC - AbsE/AbsC) 100 \quad (\text{iv})$$

Where AbsC denotes absorbance of the control and AbsE denotes absorbance of extract.

In Vitro Antidiabetic Activity by Glucose Uptake Assay by Yeast Cell

In this procedure, a baker's yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* was initially suspended in 10 mL of distilled water for 10 min and then centrifuged repeatedly at 3000 rpm for 5 min to obtain clear supernatant fluid (24). Thereafter, extract concentrations (2.5 to 40 µg/mL) were added to 2 mL of glucose solution (10 mM) and incubated in a dark cupboard for 20 min at 37 °C. After this, 100 µL of yeast suspension was added followed by shaken for 5 min, and incubated for another 60 min in the dark cupboard at 37 °C. At the end of 60 min incubation, the tubes were further centrifuged at 2000 rpm for 5 min. The amount of glucose in the supernatant was then estimated using the UV-Vis spectrophotometer (ThermoFisher, UK) at 520 nm wavelength [25]. Metronidazole 400 mg/kg (Emzor Pharmaceutical Ltd, Nigeria) was used as the standard drug. The experiment was carried out in triplicates. The amount of glucose uptake by yeast cells was then calculated using the formula below:

$$\% \text{ glucose uptake} = (Abs \text{ of extracts} - Abs \text{ of control} / Abs \text{ of extracts})100 \quad (\text{v})$$

where Abs of extracts is the absorbance of plant extracts and Abs of control is the absorbance of control reaction which contains all reagents except the plant extract).

Statistical Analysis

The data obtained where applicable were expressed as mean ± SD (n = 3) while the value of p < 0.05 was taken as statistically significant versus control using one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's post hoc. Statistical analysis was carried out using GraphPad Prism version 9.0 statistical software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the phytochemical screening of the extracts revealed the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, triterpenes/steroids, fats/oils, saponins and phenols while anthraquinones were not present (Table 1). The results further showed that the powdered *M. capitatum* leaves contain some metallic elements such as aluminium (1682.14 mg/kg), magnesium (58.22 mg/kg), sodium (76.11 mg/kg), and potassium (24.16 mg/kg) as the highest, while other heavy metals such as lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd), chromium (Cr) nickel (Ni) and manganese were completely absent (Table 2). The high amount of Al in this research corroborated with the findings of other researchers which showed that many members of the Family Melastomataceae absorbed aluminium from the atmosphere possibly with

anticorrosive effect [26]. There are several other benefits of these metals revealed in the leaf powder in the present study are have been reported [27].

Table 1. Phytochemical contents of *M. capitatum* leaf extracts

Constituent	Test	HF	EF	MF
Alkaloids	Dragendorff's	-	+	+
	Wagner	-	+	+
Flavonoids	Shinoda's	-	+	+
	NaOH	-	+	+
Tannins	FeCl ₃	-	+	+
	Goldbeater's	-	+	+
Triterpenes/Steroids	Liebermann's	+	-	-
Anthraquinones	Bontrager's	-	-	+
Fats/Oils	Spot	+	+	+
	Sudan III	+	+	+
Phenols	FeCl ₃	-	+	+
Saponins	Frothing	-	+	+

+ present, – absence, HF: n-hexane fraction, EF: ethyl acetate fraction and MF: methanol fraction.

Table 2. Metallic compositions of *M. capitatum* leaf powder.

Element	Value (mg/kg)
Aluminium (Al)	1682.14
Magnesium (Mg)	58.22
Sodium (Na)	76.11
Potassium (K)	24.16
Calcium (Ca)	8.10
Zinc (Zn)	< 0.01
Lead (Pb)	absent
Cadmium (Cd)	absent
Chromium (Cr)	absent
Nickel (Ni)	absent
Copper (Cu)	10.22
Manganese (Mn)	absent

Note: symbols in brackets represent the chemical symbols of the elements.

It has been well-researched that phenolic compounds consist of groups of plant metabolites with known antioxidant potential, this necessitate to determination of amount of this class of bioactive compounds in medicinal plants [21]. In the present study, the result showed that the total phenolic contents (TPC) in the extracts were greater than the total flavonoid contents (TFC) (Figure 1a). Because many plants have been reported as potential antioxidant sources, the

evaluation of many plants for their antioxidant effects has increased recently [14]. The TPC in plants vary among species and ecological zones in which the plants are domiciled. These phenolic compounds are capable of altering the levels of reactive oxygen species (ROS) thereby reducing their radical scavenging activities in humans [28]. The antioxidant activity of the plant evaluated has shown that the ethyl acetate fraction (EF) possessed more effect act reducing the radical scavenging activities of these ROS as shown from the DPPH and ABTS assays (Figure 1 b and c).

Figure 1: The total phenolic content (TPC), total flavonoid content (TFC) (a), DPPH (b) and ABTS (c) radical scavenging activities of *M. capitatum* leaf extracts. Results are expressed as mean \pm SD (n = 3). The value of $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant when compared to the controls using one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's post hoc test. HF: n-hexane fraction, MF: methanol fraction and EF: ethyl acetate fraction.

Figure 2: Effects of *M. capitatum* leaf extracts on glucose uptake by yeast cells in *in vitro* antidiabetic study. Results are expressed as mean \pm SD (n = 3). The value of $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant using one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's post hoc test. HF: n-hexane fraction, MF: methanol fraction and EF: ethyl acetate fraction.

The glucose transport mechanism across yeast cells has been used recently to evaluate *in vitro* antidiabetic activity of medicinal plants [25]. In the current study, there were elevated levels of glucose uptake by yeast cells in a concentration-dependent fashion as shown in Figure 2. This finding suggests that the plant extracts (HF, EF, and MF) were capable of improving the uptake of glucose thereby promoting the utilization of glucose and controlling the level of glucose in the blood. More uptake of glucose by yeast cells was witnessed in the EF than in all other extracts which might suggest that the extract (EF) contains more bioactive compounds that facilitate glucose uptake by yeast cells [24]. It has been reported that medicinal plant products acted biologically as alternative remedies for diabetes due to the presence of secondary metabolites in them (9).

For example, plants rich in metabolites such as terpenoids, flavonoids, coumarins, phenolics and sterols have been reported to help in lowering the levels of glucose in the blood which is the primary objective of most antidiabetic agents [29]. The *in vitro* antidiabetic activity of the EF and MF observed in the present study was due to the presence of these bioactive compounds.

Conclusion

The study showed that the elevated levels of glucose uptake by yeast cells suggest the anti-diabetic activity of *M. capitatum* leaf extracts. The *in vitro* activity of the plant extract was due to the presence of some secondary metabolites it contains. Thus, the result affirms the use of the plant as an ethnomedicinal prescription for diabetes in Nigeria's traditional medicine. The plant can be a good source of antidiabetic drug.

Competing Interest

We have none to declare.

Authors Contribution

U.C.A: Conceptualization, performed experiments, data collection, preparation of draft manuscript and data analysis.
M.H.H: Performed experiments, data analysis, editing and review of the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript for submission.

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